

Farmer Clusters: A landscape approach benefits natural pest control

Policy recommendations

To improve biodiversity, including natural enemies that provide important pest control services, which can reduce the need to use insecticides, the following policies are recommended:

- **Promote Habitat Diversity in Agricultural Landscapes** - Encourage the integration of a balanced mix of woody and herbaceous semi-natural habitats within and around arable farms to support the year-round persistence of beneficial natural enemies of crop pests.
- **Incentivize Crop Diversity Across Farms and Clusters** - Provide financial or regulatory incentives for farmers to cultivate a diverse range of crops, particularly those that vary in the timing of aphid or prey presence, to enhance the effectiveness of natural pest control.
- **Encourage Field Design that Enhances Ecological Connectivity** - Recommend limiting the width of crop fields where feasible to reduce the distance between crop centres and adjacent habitats. Promote the use of semi-natural habitat strips to subdivide large fields and improve ecological connectivity.
- **Optimize Semi-Natural Habitat Management for Beneficial Insects** - Develop guidelines for the design and maintenance of semi-natural habitats to ensure they offer adequate floral and prey resources during critical periods for natural enemies.
- **Minimize Insecticide Use to Protect Ecosystem Services** – Advocate for the reduction or avoidance of insecticide applications to preserve natural pest control functions and reduce negative impacts on beneficial insect populations.
- **Support Landscape-Level Coordination of Pest Management** - Promote collaborative management practices among farmer clusters to ensure that pest control strategies consider the broader landscape and the movement of natural enemies across field boundaries.

Farmer Clusters to address landscape-level solutions

Farmland biodiversity is in decline, threatening both agroecosystem services and long-term food system resilience. Farmer Clusters empower farmers to achieve their farming and environmental goals. In addition to the benefits of a “bottom-up” approach and social empowerment by working together, farmers can tackle landscape-level restoration and have a greater impact than any one individual could accomplish alone. A landscape-level approach is particularly important for restoring the pest control services for crops. The widespread conversion of agricultural landscapes into large monocultures has reduced the availability of floral resources, alternative prey, cover and overwintering sites for many organisms, including pest-regulating natural enemies. Increasing landscape heterogeneity and extending networks of non-crop habitats can restore these ecosystem services and the related functional biodiversity. If we do not want to compromise food production or economic benefits, a rational approach to such landscape restoration is needed.

Landscape ecological modelling

Empirical studies investigating the impact of diverse landscapes on pest control yield mixed results. Variation in the strength and direction of pest control responses to landscape heterogeneity limits the applicability of the results. By creating landscape-level population-dynamical models based on knowledge of predator and prey life history and behaviour, we can study which elements of the agricultural landscapes are likely most important for the natural enemies and how landscapes can be optimised for providing pest control services. As part of the **EU Horizon 2020 project FRAMEwork**, we formulated models with aphid-feeding hoverflies as the main natural enemies. In the model, the arable landscape consisted of four habitats, each providing resources for hoverflies but of different kinds or in a different period of the year. Hoverflies require prey when they are larvae and nectar and pollen when they are adults. Woody habitat provides both aphid prey and floral resources, as well as hibernation sites. Crops typically provide aphids as prey but differ in their period of growth and aphid production (represented by an early (winter wheat) and a late (potato) crop). Floral resources are largely absent in these crops and are therefore provided by flower strips in the field margins. The adult hoverflies are able to move between these four habitat types. The effect of landscape composition and habitat management was studied with spatially-implicit models, which means that the relative position of the habitats was not taken into account. To study the effect of landscape configuration, we also created spatially-explicit models, which require more computational resources.

Results and implications

For effective natural pest control, natural enemies need access to resources throughout the growing season. Our models identify when and where these resources are most critical and show how both quality, quantity and spatial arrangement of habitats influence pest suppression.

Landscape composition

- After testing various combinations, we conclude that all four habitats should be present in the local landscape for an effective suppression of aphids in the crops. The woody habitat, the flower strips and the early and the late crop are fully complementary in the timing and quality of the resources they offer to the natural enemies.
- Given the sparse presence of semi-natural habitats in our agricultural landscapes, increasing the proportions of flower strips and woody habitats both enhance pest control.
- Our results indicate that woody habitats should make up a larger part of the space for semi-natural habitats area than herbaceous habitats to maximise natural pest control, indicating the importance of woody habitats for supporting the spring generation of natural enemies with both floral and prey resources before aphids appear in the arable crops.

Landscape configuration

- Pest control in a late crop can benefit from the proximity of an early crop when they provide prey at different times of the year. This limits the precious time the hoverflies have to search aphid resources. Vice versa, an early crop can also benefit from a late crop when a woody habitat is present to bridge winter and spring.

- Proximity between woody habitats and the early crop enhances early-season control, as hoverflies and other natural enemies can reach pest-infested early crops without needing to travel far.
- Natural pest control benefits from the proximity of the four habitats included in our model, which also results in better pest control when the crop fields are narrow and bordered by both flower strips and woody habitat.

Management of semi-natural habitats

- Woody habitats more effectively support pest control when hosting many specific aphids and providing many floral resources in spring. This can be achieved by planting a good mixture of spring-flowering host species.
- Flower strips are more effective when providing high levels of floral resources for natural enemies. This can be achieved by sowing a mixture of species that produce many flowers and that have flowers with nectaries that are accessible for natural enemies.
- Flower strips are more effective when flowering in the period that the adjacent crop suffers from pest aphids. In early crops (such as winter cereals), this can be achieved by a mix of perennial flowers or by sowing annual flowers early in the year (April). For late crops (such as potato), annual flowers can be sown somewhat later.
- For the same reason, flower strips should not be mown in the period that the adjacent crop suffers from pest aphids. If needed, the flower margin of an early crop can best be mown late in the season (September), and of a late crop early in the year (before July).
- Pesticide applications compromise natural pest control, not only in the field where it is applied and in the weeks after, but also in other fields and in later years. Therefore, pesticides should only be applied when prey-predator ratios are above certain thresholds.
- Management of one field can impact natural enemy populations in nearby fields. Therefore, management should preferably be orchestrated on a larger spatial scale, such as in farmer clusters.

References / Further Reading

Mansier, L., & van Rijn, P. C. J. (2024). Modelling agricultural landscape complementation for natural pest control. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 61, 2701–2716 (<https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14790>).

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